

SIMULATION OF DAMAGE BEHAVIOR OF A HIERARCHICAL BIOLOGICAL COMPOSITE USING A CONTINUUM DAMAGE MODEL

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ABSTRACT

Dental enamel possesses extraordinary mechanical properties due to a complex hierarchical and graded microstructure. Understanding the relationship between the hierarchical structure and the flaw-tolerance behavior can be helpful for developing a new high-performance fiber reinforced composite with the desired mechanical properties. In this study, a representative volume element (RVE) is adopted to study the deformation and damage evolution process of the microstructure. A continuum damage mechanic model coupled to hyperelasticity is developed for modeling the initiation and evolution of damage in mineral fibers as well as protein matrix. In addition, debonding of the interface between fiber and matrix is captured by employing the cohesive zone model. The effect of the aspect ratio on the failure mechanisms of the composite is studied with the proposed damage model.

1 INTRODUCTION

Motivated by the outstanding mechanical properties of biological materials, such as bone, shells or wood, bio-inspired material systems with optimally tailored multiscale structures have attracted high interest for developing and synthesizing new nano-composites with an outstanding combination of several desired mechanical properties, e.g., high damage-resistance, high stiffness/weight ratio and strength [2,4].

One of the biological materials of interest is dental enamel - the hardest material in any mammal which has three hierarchical levels: bundles of nanofibers having a diameter of approx. 50 nm (level 1), multiple rods (each rod having a diameter of a few microns, level 2), and decussating bundles of rods (Hunter-Schreger bands, level 3). Due to its unique microstructure, it has an extraordinarily high fracture toughness. Therefore, it is worth to investigate and mimic the building principle of enamel for developing an advanced ceramic composite with hierarchical structure, which has an excellent combination of mechanical properties in terms of strength, stiffness and damage tolerance.

The present study focuses on the computational analysis of the relationship between the damage behavior and the specific features of the microstructure of enamel based on a 3D representative volume element (RVE). Since the protein layer transfers load between mineral fibers through large shear deformation, the damage model is formulated in the framework of finite strain theory to map the non-linear deformation behavior and degradation process of enamel in order to account for large deformations. The debonding of the interface between mineral fiber and protein is captured by a cohesive zone model, since the debonding path can be exactly predefined for the interface. The influence of the fiber length in the microstructure on the failure mechanisms is analyzed using the new damage model in order to provide suggestions for optimizing the design of man-made tailored composites.

2 CONTINUUM DAMAGE MODEL IN DENTAL ENAMEL

As already exemplified in [1], experimental studies on the fracture behavior of enamel have shown that three failure mechanisms, i.e., breaking of mineral fibers, damage of protein and debonding of protein-fiber interface, exist in enamel depending on the hierarchical level and the geometric parameters of the microstructure in the enamel. A continuum damage model is coupled to hyperelasticity in the framework of finite strains to capture the deformation and damage behavior of protein and mineral fiber in enamel. The debonding of the interface between the mineral fiber and the protein is mapped by a cohesive zone model, which has already been used in [9] and is not detailed here. The formulations of the proposed continuum damage model are outlined in this section.

We start with the existence of a Helmholtz free energy Ψ in the framework of hyperelasticity coupled with damage at finite strains. In the present version, Ψ is split into a volumetric and an isochoric part and expressed as a function of strain invariants and the isotropic damage variable D

$$\Psi(J, \bar{I}_i, D) = \Psi_{\text{vol}}(J, D) + \Psi_{\text{iso}}(\bar{I}_i, D), \quad (1)$$

where \bar{I}_i is the i -th strain invariant of the isochoric part of the symmetric Cauchy-Green tensor \mathbf{C} , and J is the determinant of the deformation gradient. In order to account for an asymmetry of damage with respect to tension/compression and also to distinguish between the effect of damage on the isochoric and volumetric part, the Helmholtz energy is written here in the form

$$\Psi(J, \bar{I}_1, D) = [1 - \alpha H(\sigma_h) D] \Psi_{\text{vol}}^0(J) + [1 - D] \Psi_{\text{iso}}^0(\bar{I}_1), \quad (2)$$

where σ_h represents the hydrostatic stress, and Ψ_{vol}^0 , Ψ_{iso}^0 are the volumetric resp. isochoric damage-free parts of the Helmholtz energy. Damage acts on the volumetric and the isochoric part in different ways: While the damage term $[1 - D]$ is fully multiplied to the isochoric part, damage is only partially applied to the volumetric energy (via model parameter α), and also only if the current load is tensile, see the Heavyside function $H(x)$.

The damage driving force Y is conjugated to the damage variable D and reads

$$Y = - \left[\frac{\partial \Psi_{\text{vol}}}{\partial D} + \frac{\partial \Psi_{\text{iso}}}{\partial D} \right]. \quad (3)$$

In order to derive the damage evolution law and determine the initiation criterion of damage, a potential function $F_{\text{dam}} = F_{\text{dam}}(Y, D, \mathbf{C})$ is defined for describing the damage process.

Via F_{dam} , the damage evolution law is derived based on the maximum dissipation principle that determines the evolution equation of internal variables

$$\dot{D} = \dot{\lambda}_b \frac{\partial F_{\text{dam}}}{\partial Y}, \quad (4)$$

where the damage multiplier $\dot{\lambda}_b$ is non-negative under loading/unloading conditions according to the Kuhn-Tucker relations. Since the damage evolution of the constituents cannot be measured in experiments at the nanoscale, a reasonable but simple assumption of the following potential function

$$F_{\text{dam}} = Y - Z(D) = Y - \left[Y_0 + \frac{1}{b} \ln \left(\frac{D_c}{D_c - D} \right) \right], \quad (5)$$

is taken here. In Eq. (5), Z is the material resistance against material damage, Y_0 is the initial resistance to damage and b is a model parameter controlling the evolution rate of damage resistance with increasing values of D . D_c represents the critical value of the damage, that is, D can take values from 0 (undamaged state) to D_c (critical state of damage leading to fracture). The damage evolution law, Eq. (4), then simplifies to

$$\dot{D} = \dot{\lambda}_b \frac{\partial F_{\text{dam}}}{\partial Y} = \dot{\lambda}_b, \quad (6)$$

In case of damage, the damage rate \dot{D} is determined by the damage consistency condition, $dF_{\text{dam}} = 0$, which by use of Eq. (5) leads to the damage evolution law

$$\dot{D} = D_c b \exp[-b(Y - Y_0)] \dot{Y}, \quad (7)$$

For the mineral fiber, which serves as the load bearing element in the microstructure of enamel, the

constitutive description for deformation and damage has to take brittle failure, i.e., microcracking, into account. The difference between tensile and compressive loading due to crack closure (usually observed in brittle materials that fail by microcracking) is considered by the parameter α and the Heavyside function in Eq. (2).

The protein transmits the load between mineral fibers and is subjected to large shear deformation. In order to model the characteristics of the deformation and damage behavior of the protein, an Arruda-Boyce hyperelastic model is used and coupled to a damage variable. Compared to the Helmholtz free energy for the mineral, the damage associated with the protein matrix is only related to distortional energy and independent of the hydrostatic pressure.

3 3D COMPUTATIONAL MODEL OF THE MICROSTRUCTURE

3.1 Geometrical model and boundary conditions

Figure. 1: Three-dimensional representative volume element with periodically staggered structure.

Enamel is composed of approx. 90% of hard hydroxyapatite fibers, which are unidirectionally aligned in the protein matrix on the first hierarchy level. In order to simplify the RVE and reduce the computational cost without loss of essential information of the microstructure, we assume that the fibers are arranged periodically in a stepped manner and represented by the prisms with a hexagonal cross-section, which in its simplest case reduces to an equilateral triangular prism as shown in Fig. 1.

According to the average size of the fiber cross section (approx. 50 nm [1]), the side length of the RVE is $S = 52$ nm in all simulations on the first hierarchical level of enamel. The thickness of the protein layer is 2 nm. The resulting hexagon side length of fiber is approximately $e_{\text{fib}} = 29$ nm. The aspect ratio ρ is defined as $\rho = L / 2e_{\text{fib}}$, where L denotes the length of fibers. In the following section, the microstructure is analyzed with varied aspect ratios ρ from 4 to 192, which correspond to fiber lengths in the range 0.22-10.8 μm .

All simulations are performed with ABAQUS/standard. Cohesive surfaces are inserted at the physical interface between protein and mineral fibers to model the interaction and the damage behavior between the protein and mineral fibers.

The 3D RVE model is subjected to a uniaxial displacement in fiber direction. Symmetric boundary conditions are applied to bottom and side faces to keep the face remaining plane and reproduce the constraint to deformation of the RVE from neighboring elements.

3.2 Material properties

The mechanical properties of enamel have been determined based on different small scale experiments. However, the elastic properties and strength of its constituents, protein and HAP, cannot directly be tested due to the limits of experimental methods. The mechanical properties of protein and HAP can only be inversely derived by combining mechanical model and experimental data.

Mineral fiber: $E=80$ GPa; $\nu = 0.23$; $\sigma^f = 2000$ MPa Protein: $E=900$ MPa; $\nu = 0.495$; $\sigma^f = 200$ MPa Interface: $T_0=60$ MPa; $\Gamma_0=1.5$ J/m ²
Material parameter in damage model of mineral: $Y_0 = 0.025$ J/mm ³ ; $b = 0.2$; $\alpha = 1$, $D_c=1$
Material parameter in damage model of protein: $Y_0 = 0.004$ J/mm ³ ; $b = 0.015$, $D_c=1$

Table 1: Mechanical properties of protein, mineral fiber and interface in enamel.

Elastic properties have already been identified in [1], strengths of the protein and the fibers were estimated in [9]. The respective values are listed in Table 1. The properties of the interface between protein and mineral (cohesive strength T_0 and fracture energy Γ_0) have also been rationalized by comparison to experiments in [9] and are given in Table 1 as well.

4 SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, the proposed damage is applied to simulate the deformation and damage behaviour of enamel at the first hierarchical level. The failure mechanisms of the composite are analyzed for various fiber aspect ratios in the range $\rho = [4 \dots 192]$.

4.1 Effect of aspect ratio of fiber

The interface between protein and mineral plays a crucial role in the overall mechanical properties of enamel due to its large area in microstructure. The parameters for the debonding of these interfaces have already been identified in [9]. The debonding shear strength $T_{deb}^S = 60$ MPa¹ is chosen here, which is weaker than the protein ($\sigma^f = 200$ MPa, leading to a shear strength of $\tau^f = \sigma^f / \sqrt{3} = 115$ MPa). The simulated stress-strain curves of the level-1-composite are displayed in Fig. 3. A high aspect ratio leads to an almost linear behavior up to sudden failure, while the stress-strain curve becomes nonlinear and the strength decreases for aspect ratios $\rho \leq 29$. The reason is the changing failure mechanism: For $\rho \leq 29$, the failure of the composite results from debonding of the interface, while fiber breaking leads to failure of the composite for $\rho \geq 39$.

Figure.2 Stress-strain response of composite with different aspect ratios.

¹ The normal debonding strength is $T_{deb}^N = \sqrt{3}T_{deb}^S \approx 100$ MPa based on the assumption of energy equivalence

The tensile strength of the level-1-composite increases nearly linearly with increasing aspect ratio for $\rho \leq 29$. The critical aspect ratio, which separates the interface or protein failure, lies between 29 and 39.

The failure mechanisms for high and low aspect ratios are detailed for two exemplary values $\rho = 4$ and $\rho = 39$ in the following. For low aspect ratio, the crack is deflected after forming a microcrack at the fiber end due to progressive debonding of the vertical interfaces, while the damage in the protein is confined to a region close to the fiber end due to its higher shear strength, see Fig. 3(a), which is accordance with experimental findings [3].

In contrast, the interface debonding is confined close to the end of the fibers for a high aspect ratio at the same macro-strain level, see in Fig. 3(b), and the microcrack is propagating from the fiber head in its original direction leading to breakage of the adjacent fibers. At this point a sharp drop in the stress-strain curve can be observed in Fig. 2 and the level-1-composite fails.

Figure.3: Damage distribution for a strain level of $\epsilon = 0.02$ in case of a weak interface for (a) $\rho = 4$ and (b) $\rho = 39$.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The stress-free fiber ends in the RVE corresponds to a main assumption in Gao's tension-shear chain model [6], that is, the protein cannot transfer any normal stress between the neighbouring fibers; the load in fiber direction can only transferred via shear across the protein. Therefore, the simulation results are compared to the analytical solution provided in Gao's model.

Fig. 5(a) plots the predicted variation of the composite Young's modulus calculated from the FEM simulations together with the analytical expression in Gao's model with respect to the aspect ratio. In Gao's model, the Young's modulus in the fiber direction can be computed by

$$\frac{1}{E} = \frac{4(1-\Phi)}{\mu_p \Phi^2 \rho^2} + \frac{1}{\Phi E_m}, \quad (8)$$

where μ_p represents the shear modulus of protein and E_m denotes the Young's modulus of the fiber. Φ denotes the volume fraction of the mineral fiber.

In the cases of an RVE without imperfection, Young's modulus is independent of the aspect ratio and corresponds to Voigt's upper bound. The small difference in the results for low aspect ratios in the range $\rho < 10$ is due to a slight variation of volume fraction of the fiber. For the simulation with imperfection, Fig. 5(a) illustrates that Young's modulus increases with increasing aspect ratio, which coincides with the prediction of Gao's model. However, the prediction of Gao's model deviates from the FEM results at large aspect ratio.

The strength of the staggered biocomposite structure σ^f can be expressed as a function of the

aspect ratio ρ in Gao's model

$$\sigma^f = \begin{cases} \frac{\Phi \rho \sigma_p^f}{2} & \rho \leq \rho_c \\ \frac{\Phi \sigma_{\text{HAP}}^f}{2} & \rho > \rho_c \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

where the critical aspect ratio ρ_c , which separates the interface or protein failure ($\rho \leq \rho_c$) from fiber failure ($\rho > \rho_c$), is defined as $\rho_c = \sigma_{\text{HAP}}^f / \sigma_p^f$. σ_p^f is the minimum value of the strength of the protein and the protein-mineral interface. In case of a weaker interface, $\sigma_p^f = T_{\text{deb}}^s$. Φ and σ_{HAP}^f denote the volume fraction and strength of the mineral fiber, respectively.

The comparison between the simulation and analytical results are shown in Fig. 5(b). The determined critical aspect ratio from the simulation is in the range 29-39, which is identical to the case without structural imperfections. The calculated critical aspect ratio by Gao's model is 34 that agrees well with the simulation results. Further, the predicted strengths of the simulations and Gao's model in case of interface failure is in good agreement for $\rho < 10$. However, the deviation increases with a increasing aspect ratio. Moreover, the predicted strength due to fiber failure is 21% higher than the computed value using Gao's model. This is caused by Gao's simplifying assumption that the shear stress is uniform along the interface between protein and fibers, which does not hold for a large aspect ratios. Additionally, Gao's model is based on a 2D micromechanical model.

Figure 5: Influence of structural imperfection and interface strength on material properties of composite. (a) normalized Young's modulus, (b) normalized tensile strength

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